

SHAPE Project Optimad Engineering srl.: RAPHI: Rarefied Flow Simulations on Xeon Phi Architecture

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Abstract

KOPPA (Kinetic Octree Parallel PolyAtomic) is a parallel numerical code for the simulation of rarefied gas dynamics. It is based on a library named PABLO (PARallel Balanced Linear Octree) used to manage octree grids in parallel. The main issue with such numerical codes is the very high execution time which can become prohibitive for some industrial applications. Thanks to the SHAPE project, important improvements have been achieved with respect to execution time and scalability. In particular, some parts of the code have been reimplemented to suit better a MIC (Multi Integrated Cores) architecture. So far, the computational time requirements have been decreased by a factor of almost 8 and a good scalability has been obtained up to 64 processors against 16 initially.

1. Introduction

The drastic increasing of computational resources during the recent decades opens new possibilities in computational simulations which start to be widely used in industries and SMEs. In this context, new codes have been implemented, targeting complex applications as for example in aerospace industry. In particular, equations for rarefied gas dynamics are really challenging because of their high number of degrees of freedom. Without particular care in the implementation, the execution time of such a code becomes prohibitive. For this reason, an efficient and highly scalable parallelization of the code is needed in order to dramatically reduce the overall computation time.

New architectures for High Performance Computing (HPC), like Multi-Integrated Cores architectures, allow the use of a very high number of cores for parallel codes. However, the implementation of such codes requires expertise in HPC and even then it remains challenging to efficiently exploit these architectures for numerical simulations. Indeed, such expertise is rarely ever present within an SME.

Therefore European projects are in a good position to support SMEs to improve numerical codes for complex applications. They give the opportunity to rethink the way codes are implemented in order to obtain decreased computational time on classical architectures, but also to port codes to new HPC architectures such as MIC. Hence, the goal is to obtain a significant gain in performance to allow simulations that were previously unaffordable.

This white paper is structured as follows: In section 2, the SME Optimad Engineering srl. is described. In section 3, new developments on the code and some important numerical results are presented.

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2. Optimad Engineering srl.

OPTIMAD engineering srl enjoys the status of being a Spin-Off company of the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering of the Politecnico di Torino, Italy.

The company develops software for scientific computing, especially in the field of fluid mechanics, and has a strong commitment to HPC.

Within this pilot project, the company's aim was to exploit the possibility of adopting in collaboration with INRIA the Intel Xeon Phi architecture for the KOPPA code.

KOPPA is used for rarefied gas simulations and is computationally expensive compared to other CFD or CAE applications.

The exploitation of the Intel Xeon Phi platform could reduce the cost of the simulations while keeping the compatibility with CPUs platform. Although a certain effort is needed to optimize the application in order to exploit the potential of the Intel Xeon Phi architecture, there is no particular additional cost in maintaining it. In general, also the application performance on CPU will benefit for the Phi-centric optimizations, too/

The overall decrease of the simulation cost would allow the usage of this code in many industries who consider this cost prohibitive.

3. Activity done.

The activity has been done on the GALILEO cluster at Cineca. It is a Linux infiniband cluster with 16 cores per node (Intel Haswell 2.4 GHz). The nodes were equipped with 2 Intel Phi 7120p accelerators with 61 physical cores (at 1.238 GHz) able to handling up the 4 threads using hyperthreading.

3.1 Description of the initial code

The initial code deals with rarefied gas dynamics. It solves a model of the Boltzmann equation named ES-BGK model (see [1]):

$$\partial f + \xi \cdot \nabla_x f = \frac{1}{\tau} (\mathcal{G}_f - f)$$

where f is a density probability function that, when multiplied with some invariant and integrated over the velocity space, gives density, momentum and energy. \mathcal{G}_f is the equilibrium function towards which the function f relaxes. Details on the model and on the numerical methods used can be found in [1], [2].

This model requires a discretization of the physical space but also of an additional space, the microscopic velocity space. The discretization of such a space is unusual in fluid dynamics and makes this problem computationally costly. Both discretizations are based on Cartesian grids but the space discretization can also be done on a hierarchical grid (octree) with dynamic refinement. This procedure is done with a library developed by Optimad Engineering named PABLO (PARallel Balanced Linear Octree). The code and the library are both written in C++ with a data parallelism and the message passing paradigm (MPI). The parallelization is done only in the physical space with a domain decomposition strategy. In the velocity space no parallelization is done. This space is usually smaller than the physical one and would require lots of collective communication that would probably degrade the scalability.

Since it is a time dependent equation, its solution is approximated using a discrete sequence of time steps. The main goal is to improve the computational time requirement of a single time step. The algorithm for one time step can be decomposed as follows:

- Creation of a local velocity grid of each cell
- Computation of the equilibrium distribution function in each cell
- Computation of the modified distribution functions to transport in each cell
- Computation of the numerical fluxes at each intersection
- Update of the distribution function value in each cell
- Integration of the macroscopic equation for the rotational temperature

- Computation of a global residual

Two main costly parts can be identified in the code: the creation of the equilibrium function (second step) and the computation of the numerical fluxes (step 4). They represent about 80% of the total computational effort.

During a typical time step several communications are done and can degrade the scalability. The first one is a « point to point » communication at step 1 to create the local grids. This kind of communication is done through PABLO that managed the grid and are non-blocking communications. The second « point to point » communication is just before computing the numerical flux. Then a collective communication is performed when computing the global residual.

During this work, the code has been tested on a simple test case with no dynamic refinement. The test case is a 2D flux at Mach 3 on a quarter of a cylinder. Most of the tests have been done on a 64 by 64 Cartesian grid in space with 21 by 21 grid points in the velocity space (also using a Cartesian grid). The behaviour of the code has also been observed increasing the load with a finer grid in space or in velocity.

3.2 Exploitation of the vectorization

A first performance study of the code on CPUs shows that the vectorization of the different loops was poorly efficient. Figure 1 shows the wall time of one time step for different compilation flag. This experiment was done on 50 time step with flag -O0 where there are no optimization effects, -O2 where the compiler starts to optimize the code, -O3 -no-vec and -fast -no-vec where the compiler optimizes the code but without vectorizing the loops and -fast where the compiler fully optimizes the code. One can note that the vectorization has almost no effect on the duration of one time step. Even worse, using the flag -no-vec to prevent the vectorization with -fast, is actually slightly faster than with -fast alone..Enabling the auto-vectorization sometimes produce two different version of the code with a runtime check to use whether or not the vectorized version of the loop. In the initial version of the code, the vectorization was so poor that it did not compensate the additional cost due to the runtime check. Therefore, the code compiled enabling the auto-vectorization becomes slower than with the -no-vec flag

Figure 1: Effect of the optimization on the initial code

It turns out that intensive loops were not written in a suitable form for compiler vectorization. Vectorization is crucial feature on Xeon Phi platforms in order to exploit the potential of the platform. That is why the first part of the work focused on this aspect.

In particular, the use of some variables inside the loops prevented the compiler to vectorize. Let us take an example of such loops. For nvtot velocity grid points, one has to compute the numerical flux. The loop was originally written as (with some variables we won't detail here see [3]):

```

for (int n=0;n<nvtot;++n)
{
    a = n%(nvmax[0]-nvmin[0]+1) +nvmin[0];
    b = n%((nvmax[0]-nvmin[0]+1) *(nvmax[1]-nvmin[1]+1))
        /(nvmax[0]-nvmin[0]+1)+nvmin[1];
    c = n/(nvmax[0]-nvmin[0]+1)/(nvmax[1]-nvmin[1]+1)+nvmin[2];

    i = a +b*vgrid.GetNpoints(0)*min(dim-1,1)
        +c*vgrid.GetNpoints(0)*vgrid.GetNpoints(min(1,dim-1))
        *max(dim-2,0);

    flux[i] = max(DotProduct(vgrid.cellCenter[i],normal),0.0)*fl[i]+
        min(DotProduct(vgrid.cellCenter[i],normal),0.0)*fr[i];

    flux[i] *= dx;
}

```

This way of implementing was not efficient because the several accesses to the vectors nvmin and nvmax and the use of the modulus operator % were preventing the vectorization. Since the set of velocity grid points can be known a priori, a vector lvgrid is created during step 1 of the time step which will be used in the loop:

```

for (int n=0;n<nvtot;++n)
{
    i=lvgrid[n];
    double d = vgrid.cellCenter[i][0]*nflux[0] +
        vgrid.cellCenter[i][1]*nflux[1] +
        vgrid.cellCenter[i][2]*nflux[2] ;
    flux[i] = std::max(d,0.0)*fl[i] +std::min(d,0.0)*fr[i] ;
    flux[i]*=dx;
}

```

Written under this form, the loop can be vectorized. We present the same graph as before for the new version of the code. It shows an important improvement of the performance.

Figure 2: Optimization effects on the new version of the code.

The results show that the auto-vectorization now has a significant effect on the execution time of one time step. The gain due to the vectorization effects is now about 10% against almost 0 in the initial version of the code. One can also note that preventing the vectorization with the flags `-O3` and `-fast` builds a slower version of the code with respect to `-O2`. This is due to some auto-vectorization of the compiler with `-O2` emphasizing the gain due to the vectorization.

One can also note that the first time step is longer than the others. This is due to the load balance process that occurs at the beginning of the first time step only. Moreover, the code has been rewritten in some part to be more efficient mostly for memory accesses. It results in faster time steps (two time faster with `-O0` and more than 3 times faster with the optimization flags).

Another difference that can be noticed is that now the duration of one time step is almost constant. This behavior is correct since the workload does not change between iterations. The increasing computational time in the initial version of the code was not expected and was probably due to some non-optimized part of the code (extra-allocation, lots of memory access, ...)

3.3 Scalability improvements

After obtaining satisfying vectorization effects, another important issue has been faced. MIC offers a large number of computational cores which are slower than the cores of a CPU. Since the code is originally parallelized using MPI, a native strategy has been chosen.

A scalability study of the initial version of the code has been done on a single Xeon Phi card. Figure 3 shows the ratio of the execution time on one process over the execution time on N processes. An ideal scalability would be a straight line with unitary slope until 60 processes (the number of physical cores). Increasing the number of processes beyond the number of physical cores (i.e. exploiting hyperthreads) will in general result in comparatively weak performance increase (if not even in decrease). Scalability is tested on two different configurations. The first one is a space grid with 2^6 points in each direction with 21×21 grid points in velocity (named 6x21). The second one uses the same velocity grid but with a space grid with 2^8 points in each direction (named 8x21) and hence increases the workload of each process.. On figure 3, we can see that the scalability degrades rapidly for more than 16 processes for the two test cases presented. Above 60 processes, the execution time stays constant. A profiling of the code with Scalasca has then been performed to identify the crucial bottlenecks.

Figure 3: Strong scalability of the code with vectorization.

It turned out that 50% of the time was spent in calls to MPI functions. In particular, some processes were waiting for this all amount of time. This was due to a bad load balance between the processes and then a large time was spent at different calls to MPI_Barrier in the code. Indeed, the load balance was initially done without any consideration of the cost of each numerical cell in the domain. The space domain was just distributed on each process in order to process the same amount of data. In our case, the scalability tests showed that this approach was not efficient. The other bottleneck of the code is the number of barriers due to the communication process. One time step was decomposed in three parts due to communications at different time.

After collapsing all the communication at the same moment in the code, an important part of the work has been devoted to estimate the cost of each part of the code. This estimation has been used to create the partition of the physical domain between the processes done by PABLO. This task has also permitted to add a new feature in PABLO, allowing to specify different weights for each cell for better load balance. Unfortunately it turned out that the evaluation of the cost for each cell depends on the partitioning. This drawback prevented us from obtaining an accurate load balance. However, the one we got was enough to dramatically reduce the time spent in MPI procedures which has been decreased from 50% on 16 processes to 10%. On figure 4, the ratios between the execution time on 15 processes and the execution time on N processes are shown for different configurations. As in figure 3, the convention for naming the different cases is « $n \times m$ » with n the level of the space grid (2^n grid points in each direction) and m the number of velocity grid points in each direction. One can observe that these modifications in the code has improved the scalability. It is clearly better up to 120 processes, which has been obtained using two MIC cards.

Figure 4: Strong scalability of the last version of KOPPA.

3.4 Curious behaviour of MPI_Barrier

The last point to focus on deals with some observations we made on the Xeon Phi architecture. For a fixed configuration, the execution time of a single time step should be constant per process and consequently the process waiting at the communication point at the first time step, should wait at the same point at each time step. Therefore, the minimal waiting time among the processes should be the sum of all barrier resolution (not necessarily zero but much smaller than the average). Performing just one time step, it has been observed that one process waits almost zero time at the barrier which is the expected behavior and corresponds to what has been observed on CPUs. Performing 10 time steps showed however that the cumulative times at the barrier for each process is in the order of tens of seconds which is too high for just barrier resolution. In the figure below two screenshots from scalasca depict this behaviour. Moreover, this phenomena does not occur on CPUs meaning that it is a phenomenon due to the MIC architecture.

Figure 5: Scalasca screenshots indicating cumulative times in MPI_Barrier; left: one time step; right: ten time steps

4. Cooperation with PRACE and benefits for the SME

The cooperation between PRACE and Optimad Engineering srl. has involved an expert from Cineca, Vittorio Ruggiero, two engineers from OPTIMAD, Marco Cisternino and Haysam Telib and one research engineer from INRIA Bordeaux Sud-Ouest, Florian Bernard.

For the computations, 5.000 core-hours on GALILEO at Cineca, Italy have been allocated to help developing the code on a Xeon-Phi architecture. The access to such an HPC machine is a crucial point for a SME to test their codes and optimize them since buying one is unaffordable.

The access to GALILEO worked well for the users and allowed small tests (compilation or very small cases) before running on more nodes. However, access to the actual resources in order to study code performance and scalability was cumbersome due to the large amount of jobs submitted on the queues.

In fact, scalability has been tested only on a very restricted numbers of nodes in order to avoid large waiting times.

There was a good and important communication between all the partners of the project resulting in nice improvements of the code and better understanding of the architecture.

5. Future plan and lessons learned

We first tested a native parallelization on Xeon-Phi architecture because it was straightforward from the initial version of the code. The project highlighted that this is probably not the best approach for such a numerical code to obtain a good scalability until 240 processes. The scalability degrades above the number of physical cores meaning that hyper threading affects the performance (as somehow expected). However, a similar behavior (but less important) is observed on CPUs meaning that hyper threading is not the only bottleneck to reach a good scalability for a large number of processes. The approximation to evaluate the cost of a cell in order to perform the load balance is probably not enough accurate. This evaluation depends on the partitioning. Hence, it is a guess that we are not able for now to set with a sufficient accuracy.

The second point to mention is the vectorization. It is an important aspect for an efficient code, in particular when running on MIC architectures. Even if the gain due to the vectorization has been improved, it is probably not sufficient to fully exploit the Xeon-Phi architecture.

However, a better understanding of this particular architecture is an important benefit for Optimad in order to build software applications better suited for HPC. All the work on the vectorization effects are profitable because it also improves the performance of KOPPA on CPUs by a factor of almost 8.

The scalability of KOPPA has been improved but more investigation is needed. In particular, we would like to understand if a hybrid approach for the parallelism could increase the scalability observed on a single MIC card. Two different hybrid parallelization can be considered: MPI+OpenMPI implementation but also MPI-3 shared memory tools. Moreover, a more important work on the profiling has to be done to understand how to improve the vectorization effects.

From an industrial point of view, the project permitted Optimad to put hands on the MIC architecture and, through the support of the computing center, to gain insight on the code and its suitability for this architecture. This type of information enables Optimad to program in a more efficient and rational way the transition to heterogeneous architectures, which is considered as a strategic development goal within the company.

6. Conclusions

All the tests and profiling performed on the code gave us the chance to dramatically decrease the computational time requirements thanks to improved vectorization and load balancing. Having access to an HPC machine gave us the opportunity to see how our code behaves at another computational scale.

Thanks to this project, KOPPA has been widely improved but also new features have been added to PABLO, a library developed by Optimad, managing the grid. Computations that were prohibitive before this projects are now possible and new applications can be done with more accuracy.

References

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